

Research

Current Trends and People's Perception Toward Lassa Fever Outbreak In Nigeria

Obameso Joseph O.^{1*} and Kuewumi Tolulope A.²

¹ Faculty of Sciences, Department of Environmental Science and Resource Management, National Open University of Nigeria, Akure Study Centre, Ondo State, Nigeria

² School of Science and Computer Studies, Department of Science Technology, Federal Polytechnic Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

***Corresponding author**

obameso_jo@fedpolyado.edu.ng

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Abstract: Lassa virus is a haemorrhagic illness linked with high morbidity and mortality in many West Africa countries resulting in about 5000 deaths annually. This study appraised trends and people's perception toward Lassa fever outbreak in Nigeria using Akure as case study. Data collected through questionnaires from respondents were analyzed to generate frequencies and proportions, and associations between variables were tested using odds ratios at 95% confidence interval (CI). The study had a response rate of 57.5% with mean age (SD) of 19±5.9. There were 56 (48.7%) males and 59 (51.3%) females. Most respondents' educational level showed that 52% had tertiary education while 41% had Secondary education. Forty-five percent (45%) of respondents were aware of Lassa fever outbreak and the major source of information was radio-television (44%). Among the determinants, occupation had the highest knowledge of Lassa fever with odd ratios (AOR) value of 4.36 at 95% CI (9.24, 2.06). The menace of COVID-19 outbreak has overshadowed the awareness of Lassa fever in Nigeria, this may suggest the increase cases of Lassa fever outbreak ever reported. Therefore, it is crucial to review the approach for controlling the spike in number and investigate the causes associated with deaths during Lassa fever epidemics.

Keywords: Akure, Epidemic, Haemorrhagic fever, Lassa virus, Mortality, Questionnaire.

1. Introduction

Lassa virus (Arenaviridae) causes Lassa fever (Lassa haemorrhagic fever-LHF). It is a haemorrhagic illness linked with high morbidity and mortality and occurs between one to three weeks after infection. It is a systemic infectious disease that can lead to acute hemorrhage as well as neurological disorders presenting a severe public health threat to some of the communities in

sub-Saharan West Africa¹. Lassa fever is endemic to most rural Nigeria and regions in Benin, Ghana, Mali and the Mano River region (Sierra Leone, Liberia and Guinea), with the disease probably existing in other West African countries as well². Lassa fever (LF) is rampant mostly in West Africa countries and some central African nations with an estimated 100,000 to 300,000 - 500,000 cases reported annually with approximately 5,000 deaths^{2, 3}. There have been reports of imported cases in countries such as Germany, United Kingdom, Netherlands and United State of America where it is not endemic^{4,5,6}. Humans contract the virus primarily through contact with the contaminated excreta of *Mastomys natalensis* rodents (Multimammate rat - natural reservoir for the virus), handling objects contaminated with rat's faeces, sleeping in rooms with severe infestation of multimammate rats or inhalation of infected particles or through body fluid. The infected rodents are capable of excreting the virus through urine, saliva, excreta and other body fluids to man⁷. Secondary transmission of the virus between humans occurs through direct contact with infected blood or body fluids. Nosocomial infection occurs mainly from transmission between health care workers and their infected patients, individuals (family members and acquaintances) with direct contact with sick patient (host) are at risk of infection. Its symptoms and signs are very similar to people suffering from fever in diseases such as malaria, viral haemorrhagic fevers such as Ebola⁸. The symptoms are mild and are often undiagnosed which may lead to multiply organ failure and eventual death within two weeks from onset. Between August 2015 and December 2016, 448 cases of Lassa fever, including 208 deaths was reported by Nigeria Center for Disease Control. 308 including 78 death was reported from Lassa fever outbreaks season in 2017. There was an unprecedented Lassa fever outbreak between the years 2017 to 2018 with 400 confirmed cases with 97 deaths in Nigeria. In 2018, NCDC reported an increase in number of infection in Nigeria, with over 633 confirmed cases with 171 deaths, while the dropped to 591 confirmed cases with 132 death. In 2020, the available record at the time of gathering this report from NCDC revealed over 1000 confirmed cases with 222 deaths⁹ (Fig. 1). Lassa fever has been a yearly occurrence since its first discovery in the year 1969 in Lassa Town and thousands of people had lost their lives or loved ones as a result of this deadly virus. Nigeria is no doubt endemic of Lassa fever¹⁰.

Figure 1: Confirmed cases of Lassa fever in Nigeria from January 2016 to September 2020.

2. Materials and methods

The research design was a descriptive type of non-experimental metropolis-based survey among residents of Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria as the study population. Study population includes individuals who have resided in the city for a period of 12 months prior to the commencement of this study. Data were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. The administered questionnaire contained information on sociodemographic variables, knowledge, belief and awareness of Lassa fever infection in Ondo State. Random sampling technique was used in this study. Information collected from the respondents was analyzed with Statistical Package in Excel 2013 version. The data were summarized using mean and standard deviation for continuous variables, frequencies, percentages for categorical variables and variables were assessed for association, odds ratio and confidence intervals (95%) were calculated for odds ratios. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant in the χ^2 analysis. Relationships between non-categorized scores were assessed using logistic regression analysis.

3. Results

Analyzed data gave a response rate of 57.5% (115 of 200), the mean age (SD) was 19 ± 5.9 years with a range of 18 to 60 years. There were 56 (48.7%) males and 59 (51.3%) females. The highest value of respondents based on religious beliefs were Christians (75.65%), followed by Muslims (23.48%) and Traditional (0.87%) respectively (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Sociodemographic variables including age, religious affiliation, marital status, education and occupation of the respondents.

Also, respondents had varied opinions according to their marital status. Married respondent value was 64.3% higher than that of single and divorced with 27.8% and 5.2% respectively. Most respondents' educational level showed that 52% had tertiary education, 41% had Secondary education while the least was 7% with primary education. Occupationally, farmers had the highest number (25%) of respondents, this was followed by traders (22%), while civil servants and students were 20% and 17% respectively. Table 1 shows the attitude and knowledge of Lassa fever among respondents. Forty-five percent (45%) were aware of Lassa fever outbreak, 42% were not aware while 13% had no knowledge of Lassa fever outbreak. The major source of information by the respondents was radio-television (44%), about 19% heard from health officials while 15% read from Newspapers or handbills. Most respondents (58%) believed that virus was the causative agents of Lassa fever, while others were of the opinion that some other microorganisms (such as bacteria and fungi) could be culpable. Observation from the mode of transmission revealed that 65% of the respondents knew that eating rat infected food could result into the spread of the virus while 27% of the respondents believed that it could spread from an infected individuals. Also, 65% of the respondents were of the opinion that LF is deadly while 28% did not agree that it's a deadly virus.

Table 1. Attitude and Knowledge of Lassa fever Among Respondents

Questions	Frequency (N=115)	%
Awareness of LF outbreak		
Yes	55	45
No	44	42
Don't know	16	13
Main source of information about Lassa		
News Paper/Pamphlets	17	15
Radio/ Television	51	44
Health Officials	22	19
Social Media	10	9
Word of Mouth	6	5
Family Member	9	8
Causes of Lassa fever		
Virus	60	58
Bacteria	33	28
Fungi	15	10
Other organisms	7	4
Transmission		
Eating rat infected food stuff	70	65
Contact with the infected persons	35	27
Through insect bites	10	8
Lassa fever is deadly		
Yes	73	65
No	30	28
I don't know	12	7
Household cooking utensils were stored away from reach of rodents		
Yes	70	64
No	35	30
I don't know	10	6
Caring for Lassa fever patient		
Yes	75	64
No	32	30
I don't know	8	6
Suspected case should be reported		
Yes	80	70
No	30	27
I don't know	5	3

Table 1. Attitude and Knowledge of Lassa fever Among Respondents (count...)

Questions	Frequency (N=115)	%
Ways Lassa fever can be prevented		
Keeping the environment clean	12	10
Ensure covering of food stuff	55	47
Getting rid of rats in the environment	25	23
Community health education	23	20
Good housing standards are a good measure for prevention of Lassa fever		
Yes	60	49
No	40	38
Not sure	15	13
Fever unresponsive to antimalarial or /and antibiotics drugs should be treated as suspected Lassa fever infection		
Yes	105	95
No	2	1
I don't know	8	4
Signs and symptoms of Lassa fever		
Pain and Sore throat	60	57
Retrosternal Cough	40	35
Bleeding manifestation	6	3
Nausea and Vomiting	4	2
Gastrointestinal Manifestation	5	3
How did you care for the sick		
Limit the number of visits to patient's	40	34
Ensure proper personal protective equipment before and after entering the patient's room	70	63
Observe safe burial practices after the death of the sick	5	3

The result in Table 2 shows the relationship between sociodemographic groups. Statistical analysis revealed that there is no significant relationship between variables (age, religion and education) as $P > 0.05$. However, marital status showed significant relationship among variables [$F(1,2)=0.01$, $P < 0.05$, $R^2=0.99$] as $P < 0.05$ ($P=0.01$). Table 3 shows the odd ratios and confidence intervals using regression analysis for determining respondents' knowledge of Lassa fever in the State. Selected determinants include age [AOR=2.02, 95% CI (5.27, 0.77)], education [AOR=1.54, 95% (CI 3.33, 0.71)] and occupation [AOR=4.36, 95% CI (9.24, 2.06)].

Table 2: Association between demographic variables

Variable	Male	female	Test Statistic
AGE			
18-25	10 (38.5)	16 (61.5)	F(1,1)=0.15, P>0.05, R ² =0.95
26-40	29 (55.8)	23 (44.2)	
41-60	17 (46.0)	20 (54.0)	
RELIGION			
Christian	40 (46.0)	47 (54.0)	F(1,1)=0.17, P>0.05, R ² =0.93
Muslim	18 (66.7)	9 (33.3)	
Traditional	1 (100)	0 (0)	
MARITAL			
Single	15 (46.9)	17 (53.1)	F(1,2)=0.01*, P<0.05, R ² =0.99
Married	31 (41.9)	43 (58.1)	
Divorced	2 (33.3)	4 (66.7)	
Other	1 (33.3)	2 (66.7)	
EDUCATION			
Primary	3 (37.5)	5 (62.5)	F(1,1)=0.27, P>0.05, R ² =0.83
Secondary	27 (57.0)	20 (43.0)	
Tertiary	28 (47.0)	32 (53.0)	

*Significant at P<0.05. 'P'=P-value, 'F'=F-test designed to test variances of the population and 'R2'= percentage of variability of the studied population predictive power of multiple regression model

4. Discussion.

This study reported the knowledge and attitude toward Lassa fever among residents of Akure metropolis, Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria. Lassa fever in the state accounts for one of the highest in the country. This study revealed that majority of the respondents were aware of on-going Lassa fever outbreak in Nigerian. Overall, the level of awareness of Lassa fever by respondents was moderately high, probably due to the greater awareness created by the Government during the outbreak of the virus. The result from this study showed that 45% of the respondents were well informed about the outbreak of Lassa fever. A similar study carried out in a nearby city (Owo), with the geographical distance of 44 km (27.3 miles) to Akure, reported 82.2% level of awareness, this is higher than the findings in this study¹¹. The main sources of information among others remained radio/television (44%) while 19% of the respondents got information from the health officials. Mass media sensitization play an important role in fighting the spread of Lassa fever, as the level of awareness during each outbreak could be a major player in achieving success over the spread of the disease. The spread of Lassa fever in Nigeria and the level of awareness raised by the Government helped to prevent the spread of the virus and that of COVID 19 during the early stage of the outbreak. Although, the threat and panic created by COVID 19 have overshadowed

Table 3 Logistic Regression Analysis

VARIABLE	OR	95% CI
AGE		
18-25		
26-40	2.02	5.27, 0.77
>41	0.67	1.57,0.29
EDUCATION		
Primary		
Secondary	0.44	2.08,0.09
Tertiary	1.54	3.33, 0.71
OCCUPATION		
Student		
Civil Servant	4.36	9.24,2.06
Trader	1.63	5.18, 0.51
Farmer	0.34	1.04, 0.11
Others	1.31	4.32,.40

*OR adjusted odd ratio at 95% Confidence interval (CI)

the prevalence of Lassa fever event, even death caused by the virus received little or no attention. Fifty eight percent (58%) of the respondents knew that virus was responsible for LF, however, some still believe that bacteria, fungi and other microorganisms cause LF. This indicates inadequate knowledge about the virus causing Lassa fever. This study corroborate the work of some researchers¹² who reported misunderstanding about the cause of LF among respondents. 65% of the respondents agreed that LF could be transmitted by eating food stuff infected with rat, while 27% and 8% respectively said contact with infected person and insect bites were the mode of transmission of the virus. Also, 65% of the respondents said Lassa fever is deadly whereas 28% did not agree with this statement. The opinions of respondents were determined to know different ways by which Lassa fever can be prevented. 47% of the respondents said the use of proper containers (rodent-proof) for food stuff is the best method for preventing LF. According to CDC, primary transmission of the Lassa virus from its rodent host to humans can be prevented in endemic areas by avoiding food, water and environment contaminated with infected rodents¹³. However, 23% of the respondents agreed on killing of rats in order to eliminate them from the environment though, the wide distribution of these rodent hosts in endemic areas in Africa makes complete control of these rodent reservoirs less feasible¹³. 10% of the respondents decided on community education and tidy environment. Cleaning of rodent infested environment and working areas should be in accordance with the guideline from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention¹⁴. Although, 49% of the respondents said that good housing standard is a good measure for preventing of Lassa fever while 65% support isolation of patients suspected/infected with LF within health facility. Furthermore, 95% of the respondents admitted that fever unresponsive to antimalarial and/or antibiotics drugs after treatment should be handled as suspected Lassa fever infection. Findings from this study showed that pain and sore throat (57%) and retrosternal cough (35%) were the major signs and symptoms of Lassa fever. In 20% of infected individuals, disease may progress to more serious symptoms including hemorrhage, respiratory distress, repeated vomiting, facial swelling, pain in the chest, back and abdomen, shock and neurological problems¹⁵. Lastly, personal protective equipment (63%) and limited visits to patients (34%) are the best ways to care for sick individuals. Standard precautions, including the use of personal protective equipment (e.g. use of goggles, high-efficiency masks, a negative-pressure room, positive-pressure filtered air respirators), frequent hand hygiene and surveillance of contacts are recommended when treating patients with Lassa fever¹³.

5. Conclusion

Nigeria witnessed a breaking record of Lassa fever outbreak than any country in the world this year while asymptomatic individuals of about 80% has been reported¹⁶. It is therefore important to scale up efforts to increase knowledge of the disease, vectors, symptoms, and prevention strategies among Nigerian people within and outside endemic communities. Effective measures for preventing the spread of Lassa fever relies on promoting good “community hygiene”, cleanliness in homes, practicing good storage system for grain and other foodstuffs, proper disposal of wastes, avoid close contact while caring for sick persons, public enlightenment and awareness about the risk factors associated with the spread of the disease. Health workers should have access to Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) against nosocomial infection of Lassa haemorrhagic fever.

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Authors' contributions:

The study design, data analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript was conceived by JOO while TAK was responsible for distribution and collection of questionnaires.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to be declared.

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